

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF INITIAL-BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM FOR ONE-DIMENSIONAL GAS DYNAMICS IN THE CLASS OF DISCONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418270>

Abstract

In this study, we will prepare a spatial auxiliary problem for the developed numerical method to solve the initial-boundary value problem for the first-order nonlinear partial differential system of equations that describes the one-dimensional motion of isentropic gas as follows:

$$u_t + uu_x = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_t + (\rho u)_x = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \rho(x, 0) = \rho_0(x), \quad (3)$$

$$u(0, t) = u_1(t), \rho(0, t) = \rho_1(t). \quad (4)$$

Keywords: numerical solutions, one-dimensional gas dynamics, discontinuous functions, isentropic gas, isentropic gas motion.

Here $u_0(x)$, $\rho_0(x)$, $u_1(t)$ and $p_1(t)$ are given functions, even may be piecewise continuous. At first we will investigate differentiable properties of the exact solution considered problem.

It is known that the solutions to this type of problem have points of discontinuity even if the initial function is sufficiently smooth. Since a discontinuous function does not satisfy a differential equation in a classical sense, it is necessary to introduce the concept of a weak solution. In order to find the weak solution, the special auxiliary problem is introduced, since it has some advantages over the main problem and permits to obtain the numerical solution in a class of discontinuous functions. Using the advantages of the auxiliary problem, some numerical algorithms are suggested that accurately exhibit the general nature of the physical processes.

Obviously, equation (2) is not dependent of $\rho(x, t)$. Therefore, the solution can be easily obtained. The solution of problems (1), (3) can be related to the solution of two particular Cauchy problems:

$$\begin{cases} u_t + uu_x = 0, \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} u_t + uu_x = 0, \\ u(0, t) = u_1(t) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The solutions of these Cauchy problems (5) and (6) are, respectively.

$$u(x, t) = u_0(\xi), \xi = x - ut \quad (7)$$

$$u(x, t) = u_1(\tau), \tau = t - \frac{x}{u} \text{ or } x = u(t - \tau) \quad (8)$$

$\xi = x - ut$ is the equation of the line whose slope is equal to u and which lies in the first quartile of the x

and t planes. This is right on. Let us now consider the characteristics passing through the t -axis, and suppose any of them pass through the point. The equation of this line will be $x = u(t - \tau)$. Also, it will be on point. This corresponds to the continuation of the characteristics passing through the points and to indicate the intersection point.

In this case, the solutions of (5), (6), (161) are combined to solve the problem

$$u(x, t) = \begin{cases} u_0(\xi), & \xi > 0 \\ \frac{x}{t}, & u_0(\xi) < \frac{x}{t} < u_1(\tau) \\ u_1(\tau), & \tau > 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

If we calculate derivatives with respect to x and t we have

$$u_x = \frac{u'_0(\xi)}{1 + u'_0(\xi)t}, \quad u_t = \frac{-uu'_0(\xi)}{1 + u'_0(\xi)t}$$

As it is seen that if $t = -\frac{1}{u'_0}$ then u_x and u_t ap-

proach to infinite. By analogy if $x = -\frac{1}{u'_1(\tau)}$ then u_x

and u_t approach to infinite too. If $\xi > 0$ and at the first point where u is breaking the derivatives u_x and u_t approach to infinite. It is mean that the solution of (9) become to multivalued function if $\xi > 0$.

Now we will construct exact solution of the problem (2),(4). For this purpose, the following is called an auxiliary problem.

$$w_t + uw_x = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$w(x, 0) = w_0(x), \quad (11)$$

$$w(0, t) = w_1(t). \tag{12}$$

is introduced. Here the function $w_0(x)$ is any

continouoa differentiable solution of $\frac{dw_0}{dx} = \rho_0(x)$ equation. Let us assume that (10) is valid at point $x = 0$. Then we have

$w(x, t) = -\int_0^t u(x, \tau)\rho(x, \tau)d\tau$, and from this we get

$$w(0, t) = -\int_0^t u_1(\tau)\rho_1(\tau)d\tau \equiv w_1(t). \tag{13}$$

Theorem . If $w(x, t)$ is solution of problem (10), (12) then the function obtained by

$$\rho(x, t) = \frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial x} \tag{14}$$

is soft solution of main problem (2)-(4).

As analogy the solution of problem (10), (12) can be related to the solution of two particular Cauchy problems:

$$\begin{cases} w_t + uw_x = 0, \\ w(x, 0) = w_0(x) \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \iint_{R_+^2} \left\{ \phi_t(x, t)u(x, t) + \phi_x(x, t) \frac{u^2(x, t)}{2} \right\} dxdt + \\ & \int_0^\infty u_0(x)\phi(x, 0)dx + \int_0^T u_1(t)\phi(0, t)dt = 0, \\ & \iint_{R_+^2} \left\{ \phi_t(x, t)\rho(x, t) + \phi_x(x, t)u(x, t)\rho(x, t) \right\} dxdt + \\ & \int_0^\infty \rho_0(x)\phi(x, 0)dx + \int_0^T \rho_1(t)\phi(0, t)dt = 0. \end{aligned}$$

In order to find of the weak solutions the following auxiliary problem are introduced

$$\frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial x} \right)^2 = 0, \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial t} + u(x, t) \frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial x} = 0, \tag{19} \\ & v(x, 0) = v_0(x), u(0, t) = u_1(t), \end{aligned}$$

$$w(0, t) = \rho_0(t), \rho(x, 0) = u_1(t).$$

Here the functions $v_0(x)$ and $w_0(x)$ are any continuously differentiable solutions of these eqationns

$$\begin{cases} w_t + uw_x = 0, \\ w(0, t) = w_1(t). \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

The solutions of which are

$$w(x, t) = w_0(x - ut) \equiv w_0(\xi), w(x, t) = w_1\left(t - \frac{x}{u}\right) = w_1(\tau).$$

Combine these solutions of Cauchy problem we get

$$w(x, t) = \begin{cases} w_0(\xi), & \xi > 0 \\ w_1(\tau), & \tau > 0 \end{cases}$$

When $\xi > 0$ for derivative w_x we found

$$\rho(x, t) = \frac{\rho_0(x - ut)}{1 + t\rho_0'(x - ut)}. \tag{17}$$

The results obtained show that both solutions of problems (1), (3) and (2)-(4) are multivalued. Therefore, this problem has no classical solution, and its weak solution is defined as follows.

Definition: The functions $u(x, t)$ and $\rho(x, t)$ satisfying of the initial and boundary conditions (3), (4) are called weak solutions of the problem (1)-(4), if following integral relations are valid for any test functions

$$\frac{dv_0(x)}{dx} = f(x), \frac{dw_0(x)}{dx} = g(x)$$

Theorem . If $v(x, t)$ and $w(x, t)$ are solution of the auxiliary problems then defined by

$$u(x, t) = \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial x}, \rho(x, t) = \frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial x}$$

Functions are weak solution of the main problem.

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